

Supply Chain Management and Operational Performance of Unilever Indonesia

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Abstract

Unilever, is a multinational company which sells consumer goods such as beverages, culinary items, cleaning supplies, and personal hygiene items. Unilever NV, located in Rotterdam, and Unilever PLC, based in London, make up the dual-listed company Unilever. The company is among the top global providers of food and beverage, personal care, and beautyproducts. Its products are sold in more than 190 countries and it serves 2.5 billion people everyday. This paper explores how supply chain affect the operational performance of Unilever Indonesia. A number of systems are thoughtfully created to provide outcomes that are both efficient and successful. Beginning with the first raw material supply, theproduct is produced, then it is distributed till it is received by customers. Through the implementation of strategic performance management techniques, Unilever is able to manufacture goods that are customized to meet the demands of its customers. The strategy used by Unilever highlights how crucial a well-thought-out and well-implemented supply chain strategy is to success.

Key words:Supply Chain Management, Supply Chain Strategy, Performance, Unilever

Introduction

Unilever, is a multinational company which sells consumer goods such as beverages, culinary items, cleaning supplies, and personal hygiene items. Unilever NV, located in Rotterdam, and Unilever PLC, based in London, make up the dual-listed company Unilever. The company is among the top global providers of food and beverage, personal care, and beautyproducts. Its products are sold in more than 190 countries and it serves 2.5 billion people everyday. Dove, Knorr, Dirt Is Good, Rexona, Hellmann's, Lipton, Wall's, Lux, Magnum, Axe, Sunsilks, and Surf are just a few of Unilever's over 400 brands. A crucial component of Unilever's supply chain strategy is supply chain optimization. The business looks for areas in its supply chain where it may reduce costs and boost efficiency by using analytics and data- driven insights. Among Unilever's supply chain optimization projects are inventory level reduction, waste elimination, and process simplification. With the use of these tactics, Unilever may cut expenses while increasing revenue.

Cooper (1997) noted that the phrase "supply chain management," or SCM, did not exist until the early 1990s. The term "supply chain management" refers to a group of management tasks involving the movement of resources, information, and materials within an organizational network that are organized from upstream to downstream, or from the earliest natural raw materials to completed goods in the hands of customers. Applying the notion of supply chain management to a business aims to boost productivity, provide value, and satisfy clients. Based on the study of (Oktalia et al, 2022), shows that The ERP and SCM strategies used by PT Nestle Indonesia have contributed to the company's success in growing and becoming a renowned

manufacturer of food and beverage products. Supply Chain Management (SCM) may enhance business operations through a variety of implemented tactics. SCM is being implemented in different organizations and institutions with excellent results. As previously mentioned research explains, supply chain management (SCM) is a management concept that will facilitate business operations. In order to improve Unilever Indonesia's business operations, researchers will examine the supply chain management strategy in this study

Literature Review

Supply Chain Management

In order to improve the long-term performance of both the individual companies and the supply chain as a whole, supply chain management, or SCM, is broadly defined as "the systemic, strategic coordination of the traditional business functions and the tactics across these business functions within a particular company and across businesses within the supply chain." (Mentzer et al., 2001, p.18). The supply chain is also dynamic as there is a continuous movement of funds, products and information between its many stages. The objective of the supply chain is to optimize the total value created, which is defined as the difference between the value of the final product that consumers get and the expenses that the supply chain incurs in order to satisfy those customers' demands. According to Chen and Paulraj (2004), a typical supply chain is a network of processing linkages for resources, information, and services that has supply, transformation, and demand characteristics. A strategy or design will be used in the supply chain to help establish the supply chain process that will be produced. Decisions made in the supply chain include where to put locations and facilities, what to stock, how to transport goods, and information systems, all of which must support the goals of the supply chain itself.

The cycle view and the push or pull view are the two perspectives that make up the supply chain process view. The supply chain process' cycle view is broken down into multiple segments. The stages from suppliers to consumers are similar to the initial stage, which is the cycle of customer orders, replenishment, manufacturing, and procurement. This cycle will be repeated at each level to meet the needs of the customer, and each level has its own process with distinct roles and responsibilities created in each process. According to the push or pull perspective, there are two ways to handle supply chain processes: push involves carrying out customer orders while continuing to produce finished goods, and pull involves delaying a product until a customer requests it, allowing you to receive the order first and then fill the void in the product line. To optimize the supply chain strategy, we must first consider the nature of the company's operations, since each of these two approaches has pros and cons of its own.

Achieving Strategic Fit, Supply Chain Performance & Supply Chain Drivers

The first part of this theory will cover how businesses operate in a competitive environment and choose their supply chain strategy. It goes without saying that a company needs a strategy of its own in order to compete and survive in the marketplace. Different strategies will yield different outcomes and methods for achieving the company's objectives, and these factors will decide whether the company's chosen course of action will be effective in competing with rivals or meet the needs of its customers. The consistency between the supply chain capabilities that the supply chain strategy seeks to develop and the customer demands that the competitive strategy seeks to meet is referred to as the "strategic fit" between the two strategies. Chopra and Meindl (2001), stated that no single role can ensure the chain's success. Nonetheless, the chain as a whole could fail if one link fails. According to Chaharsoogi & Heydari (2011, p.331), There are two main elements that constitute strategic fit: (1) the customer's expectation, which is the main building block of the "competitive strategy" of a supply chain and (2) the supply chain

performance, which is associated with the “supply chain strategy” in responding to established competitive advantage. All process and functions of the company’s value chain will contribute to the success or failure of the company and these functional processes do not operate separately which can ensure the success of the supply chain or even failure of the supply chain within the company. The success and failure of companies in determining strategic fit are in the following ways:

- 1) Competitive and functional strategy must be able to form harmony in the overall strategy and well coordinate.
- 2) Companies with different functions must be able to utilize resources and strategies well so that they run smoothly.
- 3) The entire supply chain design and the roles within it must be aligned in order to better support the supply chain strategy. So, there are two steps to achieve strategic fit:

In this stage, companies must be able to understand demand uncertainty by understanding how much must be produced for consumers, what is the consumer’s response, what are the product variations and prices, this can be change according to the company’s external conditions.

Expanding Strategic Scope

At this stage, the company must understand how the company itself can meet the demand and the capacity of the company’s supply chain capabilities, supply chain effectiveness and cost responsiveness. Expanding strategic scope or the scope of strategic fit is a theory that refers to the functions within the company and stages throughout the supply chain that have been arranged in an integrated and objective manner where on the other hand each operation will have its own functional area and design their own strategy individually and independently with the aim of optimizing performance.

Supply Chain Performance and Drivers

According to Hausman (2002), supply chain performance refers to the extended supply chain’s activities, in meeting end-customer requirements, including product availability, on-time delivery, and all necessary inventory and capacity in the supply chain to deliver that performance in a responsive manner. Since supply chain performance encompasses raw materials, components, subassemblies, completed goods, and distribution via several channels to the final consumer, it transcends organizational borders. Additionally, it transcends the boundaries of conventional functional organization categories including production, distribution, marketing & sales, procurement, and research & development. SCM Drivers will address is the supply chain’s drivers, which include globalization, information technology advancements, and empowered customers. Because supply chain drivers are heavily reliant on customers, there are three different categories for supply chain concepts: system, total cost, and trade-off boundaries of conventional functional organization categories including production, distribution, marketing & sales, procurement, and research & development. Chopra and Meindl (2001), introduce the logistical and cross-functional drivers representing Supply Chain drivers as the facilities, inventory, transportation, information, sourcing and pricing.

Discussion

Background of Unilever Indonesia

Since its founding on December 5, 1933, Unilever Indonesia has developed into one of the country’s top manufacturers of fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) which are products that are

constantly present in people's daily lives and include brands like Pepsodent, Lux, Lifebuoy, Dove, Sunsilk, Clear, Rexona, Vaseline, Rinso, Molto, Sunlight, Wall's, Royco, Bango, and many more. With operations in more than 80 countries worldwide.

PT Unilever Indonesia requires a more integrated system that enables strategic policy creation to enhance both internal and external business processes, in addition to enabling monitoring of each branch in each country. For the reason, PT Unilever Indonesia ought to establish a well-thought-out system, namely a supply chain management system. Simultaneously, Unilever's commitment to sustainability poses a significant challenge: integrating their environmental effect from raw material procurement, through processing and production, and ultimately to product consumption and disposal by consumers (Dhawan et al., 2010).

Supply Chain of Unilever Indonesia

When discussing the key strategic activities that occur in every manufacturing organization, the process of supply chain management, or SCM, is unquestionably highlighted. Because SCM is so important to every firm, its significance has grown in the modern period. Supply chain management used to be viewed as a support department inside any company, but because of the extensive role it plays in a company's operations, it is now regarded as one of the main departments. In the current business environment, characterized by intense rivalry, it is imperative for every organization to build and maintain an efficient and effective supply chain management system in order to thrive.

- 1) **Planning:** Forecast the patterns of current and future product purchases made by consumers. The factories that will carry out manufacturing, the suppliers that will supply raw materials, and the packaging will all be connected by this forecast.
- 2) **Procurement:** Establishing sound connections with important suppliers and making smart judgments about the procurement of packaging, raw materials, and indirect costs.
- 3) **Manufacturing:** Recognize how to adapt to fluctuations in demand, maintaining a constant emphasis on efficiency, and maximizing the appropriate manufacturing output at the appropriate cost while upholding the highest standards of quality.
- 4) **Logistic:** Ensuring timely delivery of finished goods that meet quality standards for every brand with a minimum of 400 worldwide

PT. Unilever Indonesia to meet the needs of many customers, so with a push strategy, the

production process will produce a certain number of products at a certain level and then the products will be moved to the warehouse, after which the number of products will be sent according to what consumers need (pull). The combination of these two methods causes the possibility of a stock out to be very small, because using the push strategy causes the amount of inventory in the warehouse to be greater, and using pull causes the amount of inventory in the depot to be less (cheap holding costs), but if the depot requires more quantity, the warehouse can immediately provide it without waiting for the production process again. Implementation of supply chain system integration with a combination of these two methods can increase the efficiency of using resources and labor, due to reducing waste of excess inventory in retail and depots and utilizing materials as much as possible, so that the integration of these two methods increases the efficiency of Unilever's supply chain itself.

Unilever’s Supply Chain Workflow

In product manufacturing, Unilever has many manufacturing companies to make its products. The manufacturing company obtains raw materials to make products from suppliers of the required raw materials. In product distribution, Unilever products are finished and ready to be marketed, but before that the products are stored in warehouses to plan the scheduling of products that will be distributed by distributors so that the products can reach final consumers.

Unilever uses a wide range of manufacturing firms to produce its goods. Suppliers of the necessary raw materials are where the manufacturing business gets the raw ingredients to produce products. Before being finished and prepared for marketing, Unilever's products are held in warehouses to help with product distribution scheduling. This ensures that the items reach their intended end users on time. Distributors have the ability to provide stores like Indomart, Transmart, Hypermart, and others with these items. In addition, distributors may choose to distribute it via consumer retail agents or wholesalers.

Unilever Strategic Fit Implementation

Strategic fit is a meeting between company strategy and supply chain strategy. In running the company having the right strategic fit encourages Unilever to utilize all factors efficiently to get the best such as using enormous production capabilities to develop in many regions especially in Indonesia.

- 1) Because society is ever-changing, PT Unilever has the capacity to

foresee trends in addition to having an awareness of them in order to keep a competitive edge.

- 2) In addition to collaborating with partners in the supply chain to produce innovation in goods and packaging, PT Unilever works with governments, non-governmental organizations, and other stakeholders to achieve change that is beneficial for society and business. R&D's goal is to use innovation to create brands by capitalizing on the advantages that science and technology have to offer.

Drivers of Supply Chain Process

- 1) Manufacture Facilities

PT Unilever has facilities spread throughout many cities. The headquarters are situated in Jakarta. Because Jakarta is the capital of Indonesia, the location of the Head Office was chosen. Other places are then separated according to the kind of goods. For instance, soya and sauce ingredient production at the Subang plant.

In order to adapt production levels to meet market demand, Unilever's manufacturing department employs a push approach utilizing aggregate planning and aggregate customer demand projection data obtained from retailers and warehouses.

Unilever has a commitment to making sustainability a main element in its business is realized through innovation in the packaging of its products. Unilever has innovated several products, such as the Molto Once Rinse product, which can save up to 75% water when washing clothes, and the smaller bottle caps for Sunsilk shampoo and conditioner products, which contribute to the reduction of 123 tons of plastic waste annually (Unilever, 2016).

- 2) Warehouse

Raw Material Store (RMS) is a material storage place. Currently PT. Unilever Indonesia implements warehouse management for RMS management. Warehouse management aims to manage RMS operations and indirectly aims to reduce costs within RMS. Warehouse management is carried out to optimize RMS capacity, increase inventory accuracy, increase RMS capacity, increase RMS worker productivity and to reduce costs from incoming materials to finished goods

Besides RMS, Unilever also utilizes a stock keeping unit (SKU) system to manage the warehouses where it distributes its resources and goods. The system's goal is to make the process of determining production plans simpler and more lucid. Using a SmartOPS Enterprise Inventory Optimization tool, Unilever leveraged SmartOps EIO technology to optimize the amount of inventory required by the business. The data needed is in the form of historical data, cost factors, and promotions, which will later be managed into optimal inventory and stock keeping units. Based on the management results, Unilever can determine week cover and safety inventory that they use. This application assists Unilever's company operations in easily calculating the required inventory levels.

- 3) Logistic

Because distributors or retailers hold the inventory of PT Unilever items

rather than the manufacturer or factory directly, the suggested logistics network offers storage with carrier delivery distribution. The Company also digitizes the Company's distribution system called Digital Logistics. Through this endeavor, the company may increase the quality of its services while cutting expenses. The business also employs big data analysis to support targeted marketing campaigns and the production of high-quality communication materials. There are several strategies that are implemented by Unilever based on research by (Hernanta, 2018),

- a. Due to direct demand from numerous outlets, an intensive distribution strategy will be used, meaning that the distribution process will be completed daily and completely to all outlets. In addition, the distributor aims to have a certain number of outlets since higher outlet counts translate into more revenues for the distributor.
 - b. This distributor's distribution method involves receiving products from the factory and distributing them to certain distributors and retail locations. Products kept in stock in the distributor's warehouse are then transferred by the distributor via trucks to wholesalers and retailers, who in turn deliver them directly to end consumers.
- 4) Transportation
- Cross-docking is an SCM system or delivery process improvement approach that Unilever uses in its supply chain. In places with limited space, this approach can expedite delivery while reducing labor and warehousing

expenses. The delivery process involves the utilization of air, land, and marine transportation.

5) Information

These triggers are information and analysis on the supply chain's facilities, inventory, transportation, costs, pricing, and customers. Since information directly affects each trigger and aids management in enhancing supply chain chances to increase efficiency, it has the greatest potential to improve supply chain performance. Because information technology support is so important, Unilever switched from using the BPCS (Business Process and Control System) system to the SAP system in January 2009.

In addition to serving as a venue for purchases and sales, Unilever views retailers as a source of information about client demands (demand data). Through merchants, Unilever is also able to track changes in the interests and requirements of the local community.

6) Sourcing

The decision of who or what portion of the supply chain activity such as manufacturing, storage, transportation, or information management will be used as this trigger. These choices determine the company's success and the functions it outsources at the strategic level.

When choosing suppliers, Unilever works with people who live nearby the factory and those who are local suppliers. Local vendors that supply specific raw materials have also complied with the business partner and sustainable agricultural codes. In addition, the supplier needs to meet the standards of the QMS (Quality Management System), which are specifications that Unilever has set upon its own. The third party that Unilever has designated to conduct audits will work with suppliers to carry out the QMS that will be adopted. For high-risk materials, this audit activity is conducted every 12 months, and for low-risk materials, it is done every 24 months.

7) Pricing

The amount that a business will spend on products and services in the supply chain is determined by this trigger. Each supply chain trigger interacts with other triggers to establish the efficiency and capacity of the organization to respond. This trigger structure therefore establishes if and how it affects supply chain performance.

8) Role of Digital Technologies in Unilever

They are able to make supply chains more transparent and traceable because to the technology's increased visibility into them. As this is where the biggest danger of deforestation resides, it enables the corporation to observe and understand what's happening to forests globally, including the crucial "first mile" from where raw materials are generated to where they are first processed. In order to test and implement cutting-edge technologies, such as satellite imagery, artificial intelligence, and geolocation data, Unilever is working with partners.

Unilever Distribution Network

Unilever offers two options for shipping its products to clients that have several distribution hubs. Products can be distributed in a centralized or decentralized manner to a specific client.

Centralized delivery refers to the process of moving goods from Unilever DCs to a single customer DC, or a single delivery site. Decentralized delivery refers to the process of transporting goods from Unilever distribution centers to individual client distribution centers, or various delivery sites.

Unilever Supply Chain Performance

- 1) **Resources:** PT Unilever purchases agricultural raw materials as part of many annual procurement initiatives. Sustainable resources make about 60% of it.
- 2) **Production:** According to Gartner, PT Unilever has the best FMCG supply chain in the world. PT Unilever runs 300 plants and has made significant investments in eco-production and efficiency.
- 3) **Sales:** In order to succeed in the market, PT Unilever collaborates with retailers to make sure that our products are consistently accessible and attractively presented across all platforms, including supermarkets and online shopping.
- 4) **Inventory Levels:** The Unilever supply chain strategy has enhanced productivity and customer support for the business. Unilever has improved its responsiveness to client demand and shortened lead times by using a worldwide network of suppliers. Unilever prepares shipments according to prearranged schedules in order to keep inventories at predetermined levels. As the result, company may gradually decrease inventory levels at the retail store or distribution center as long as service levels are met.
- 5) **Customer Satisfaction:** Customers are now more satisfied and receive their products faster as a consequence of this enhanced customer service. Furthermore, by ensuring that its products are continuously available to clients, Unilever has been able to lower the risk of stock-outs through the implementation of a supply chain strategy.

Technology on Unilever Supply Chain

Industry 4.0 and digitalization are examples of disruptive breakthroughs that have an impact on the creation of new supply chain management (SCM) concepts, principles, and models. Digital supply chains (SCs) and smart operations may be developed more easily thanks to the Internet of Things (IoT), cyber-physical systems, and smart, linked items (Ivanov et al., 2019). Based on

research by (Anitah et al., 2019), concluded that with the use of Industry 4.0 technologies, Unilever's operational performance metrics such as product quality, delivery lead-time, flexibility, delivery dependability, manufacturing lead-time, and productivity levels markedly increased. The main benefits of Industry 4.0 technologies, such as the gathering of big data about the supply chain, error elimination, increased supply chain visibility, operational efficiency improvements, employee motivation, and order customization, are responsible for the improvement in operational performance. Automation technologies have helped Unilever decrease human error, increase productivity, and automate repetitive activities in the logistics industry. Examples of these technologies include artificial intelligence and machine learning. Automation is another tool Unilever utilizes to improve supply chain inventory management.

Conclusion

This paper explores how supply chain affect the operational performance of Unilever Indonesia. A number of systems are thoughtfully created to provide outcomes that are both efficient and successful. Beginning with the first raw material supply, the product is produced, then it is distributed till it is received by customers. Through the implementation of strategic performance management techniques, Unilever is able to manufacture goods that are customized to meet the demands of its customers. The strategy used by Unilever highlights how crucial a well-thought-out and well-implemented supply chain strategy is to success.

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